

 Article

Put on a open (max 2) or closed (max 1)
Project on the table

Fame for writer: 2

Fame for Project owner: 1

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 Papermill Article

This Article does not require a Project

Fame 3

 Plagiarism

Substitute an Article written by another player with this card.
-2 Fame for the other player.

Fame 3

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